

FLIPPED CLASSROOM AND CERTIFICATE COURSES FOR STUDENT EDUCATION IN INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING

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Abstract

Purpose – *Flipped classroom is an instructional approach that reverses the traditional order of teaching and learning, by delivering the content online before the class and engaging the students in active learning during the class*

Methodology/approach - *This paper reviews the literature on the use of flipped classroom concepts and certificate courses in student education and reports from practical implementation in study programmes of industrial engineering.*

Findings – *The paper identifies the benefits, challenges, and best practices from literature and practical implementation.*

Research limitations/implications – *Flipped classroom is an instructional approach that reverses the traditional order of teaching and learning, by delivering the content online before the class and engaging the students in active learning during the class. Certificate courses are short-term, focused, and flexible learning opportunities that can enhance the students' skills and competencies in specific domains.*

Practical implications – *Flipped classroom concepts and certificate courses are short-term, focused, and flexible learning opportunities that can enhance the students' skills and competencies in specific domains.*

Originality/value – *The paper provides examples of the successful implementation of several courses in the study programme of industrial engineering on both, bachelor and master levels.*

Key words: *flipped classroom, certificate course, student education*

Introduction

The rapid development of information and communication technologies (ICT) has transformed the landscape of education, creating new opportunities and challenges for both teachers and learners. One of the emerging trends in education is the use of flipped classroom concepts, which aim to enhance the quality and effectiveness of teaching and learning by shifting the focus from passive to active learning. Another trend is the use of certificate courses, which offer flexible and personalized learning pathways for students who want to acquire or update their skills and competencies in specific areas. Both flipped classroom concepts and certificate courses have the potential to improve the student outcomes and satisfaction, as well as to meet the changing needs and expectations of the labor market and society.

However, the implementation of flipped classroom concepts and certificate courses is not without challenges, such as the need for adequate preparation, support, and evaluation, the possible resistance from some teachers and students, and the issues of quality assurance and

recognition. The paper will review the existing literature and evidence on the use of flipped classroom concepts and certificate courses in student education, and to identify the best practices and recommendations for their successful integration.

Flipped Classroom Concepts and Certificate Courses: An Overview

Flipped classroom is an instructional approach that reverses the traditional order of teaching and learning, by delivering the content online before the class and engaging the students in active learning during the class (Bergmann & Sams, 2012), (Abeysekera & Dawson, 2015), (Lage, Platt, and Treglia 2000).

The flipped classroom concept is based on the premise that students can learn the content at their own pace and place, and use the class time for more interactive and collaborative activities, such as discussions, problem-solving, case studies, and projects, that require higher-order thinking skills and teacher guidance (Bishop & Verleger, 2013). The flipped classroom concept also aligns with the constructivist and social learning theories, which emphasize the active and social construction of knowledge by the learners, rather than the passive and individual transmission of knowledge by the teachers (Kim, Kim, Khera, & Getman, 2014). Moreover, the flipped classroom concept supports the principles of universal design for learning (UDL), which aim to provide multiple means of representation, engagement, and expression for diverse learners, and to reduce the barriers and increase the opportunities for learning (Meyer, Rose, & Gordon, 2014). However, the flipped classroom concept is not a one-size-fits-all approach, and there are different ways to implement it, depending on the goals, context, and resources of the teachers and learners. For example, some flipped classroom models may use a hybrid or blended format, where some of the content is delivered online or face-to-face. (O'Flaherty & Phillips, 2015). Some flipped classroom models may use a synchronous or asynchronous mode (Chen, Wang, Kinshuk, & Chen, 2014) where activities might be customized and tailored to the individual needs and preferences of the students (Zainuddin & Halili, 2018).

Certificate courses are short-term, focused, and flexible learning opportunities that can enhance the students' skills and competencies in specific domains. Certificate courses are usually offered by educational institutions, professional associations, or online platforms, and they can be accredited or non-accredited, depending on the quality standards and recognition criteria of the providers and the stakeholders (Buckley, 2018). Certificate courses can be classified into two main types: credit-bearing and non-credit-bearing. Credit-bearing certificate courses are part of the formal education system, and they can be integrated into the degree programs or taken as standalone courses, depending on the admission and graduation requirements of the institutions. Non-credit-bearing certificate courses are part of the informal or non-formal education system, and they can be taken for personal or professional development, without any prerequisites or credentials (Chen, 2016). Certificate courses can be delivered in various formats and modes, such as face-to-face, online, or blended, and synchronous, asynchronous, or mixed. (Oliver, 2019).

Comparison and Complementarity of Flipped Classroom Concepts and Certificate Courses

Flipped classroom concepts and certificate courses are both innovative and flexible approaches to education, that can offer multiple benefits for the students, such as increased motivation, autonomy, and achievement, as well as enhanced skills and competencies in specific domains. However, they also have some differences and limitations, that need to be considered and addressed, such as the need for adequate preparation, support, and

evaluation, the possible resistance from some teachers and students, and the issues of quality assurance and recognition.

The use of certificate courses in student education is an innovative form of learning that is geared towards the needs and interests of learners. Certificate courses are short, thematically focused courses that can be offered online or face-to-face. They aim to provide learners with specific competences or qualifications that they need or want to enhance for their professional or academic career. Certificate courses can be taken as part of a regular degree program or as additional continuing education.

The following SWOT analysis identifies the main similarities and differences between flipped classroom concepts and certificate courses. A detailed overview of the results can be found in figure 1 and 2 at the end of this paper. The analyses are based on the following authors: Bishop and Verleger (2013), Lo & Hew (2017), O'Flaherty & Phillips (2015), Baturay et al. (2019), Chen et al., (2013, 2014), De Coi et al. (2007), , Govaerts et al. (2012), Zainuddin & Halili (2016), Fussenecker et al. (2023) and Niemann et al. (2009, 2022, 2023, 2024), Littlejohn et al. (2016), Milligan et al. (2017), Nawrot & Doucet (2014).

As the figures 1 and 2 show, flipped classroom concepts and certificate courses have some common strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, as well as some unique ones. Therefore, it is possible to combine and integrate the two approaches, in order to maximize their advantages and minimize their disadvantages, and to create more effective and efficient learning experiences for the students. For example, flipped classroom concepts can be used to deliver the content of certificate courses online, before the class or the assessment, and to engage the students in active learning during the class or the assessment. Certificate courses can be used to provide flipped classroom concepts with more focused and flexible learning opportunities, that can enhance the students' skills and competencies in specific domains.

Development of course modules and training programs

Several flipped classroom courses have now been developed at Flix at Duesseldorf University of Applied Sciences in the field of industrial engineering education, which are used as course and teaching formats for the training of students in the area of elective subjects, but also in compulsory subjects.

Service Engineering course module:

The challenges outlined above place enormous demands on the developers of services in the future. Therefore, the goal was to develop a consistent methodology for the development of services, which takes up and implements these requirements. In this context, a training course was developed at the Flix Research Centre for Life Cycle Excellence at the University of Applied Sciences Duesseldorf. The target group of the course are engineering students and professionals (see Figure 3). The course teaches the basics of designing and developing modern services using "hands-on" training modules. Figure 4 shows a rough overview of the topics, methods and practical parts of the course contents. The course participants develop and design a service step by step using methods and tools that are learned and tested within the course. In this way, the course participants simultaneously learn the methodological tools in a creative course atmosphere. The course lasts approximately five days and can be extended or shortened on a modular basis depending on the group of participants and the objectives. At the end of the course, in addition to the presentations of the developed services, there is also an examination of the theoretical basics (online examination). The course is also suitable for delivery in an online format. However, experience has shown that a face-to-face format is advantageous due to the numerous group work and practical interactions. The course language and the teaching materials are in English.

Business models and entrepreneurship course module:

In this course, students are introduced to the development of business models and business plans in group work. The courses consist of brainstorming workshops in the initial phase of the course and are then continued in small groups of 4-5 students each for detailed elaboration. While the initial phase (brainstorming) is still moderated centrally by the lecturer for all course participants, the further detailed development takes place in small groups with weekly meetings in which the lecturer takes on the role of a coach. At the meetings, the students present their work progress to the lecturer, who supports the group with suggestions, critical questions and advice. The students take the active part in the discussions, the lecturer only takes on the role of a coach. The group members also plan the next work steps independently and thus also determine the pace of work in the group. Documents on the sub-topics to be worked on as well as deadlines and submissions are available centrally (in TEAMS) for all course participants. The path to the goal as well as the distribution of tasks and deliverables are determined individually within the group by the group members. The central instructions also contain information on the examination papers to be submitted, but the content and type of presentation is also determined by the group members. The assignments are designed as semester tasks. The module handbooks for the courses have been adapted accordingly. For formal reasons, however, the examination performances must be organised in such a way that it is possible to assign the performances to the individual group members at a later date.

Course module Methods of Production Optimization:

This course module is used in the Master International Industrial Engineering program. The aim is to enable students not only to master lean management methods in theory, but also to master some methods "hands-on" and to be able to apply them using practical examples. To this end, the course participants are also divided into small groups with the task of developing a training program for a methodology for the other course members. In particular, the training program should focus on the practical mastery and practice of a method. The methodology is then carried out in a final examination under the direction of the students as a training team with the other course participants on the basis of a self-designed practical exercise. After completing the course, students also receive a certificate from the FLiX-Institute confirming that they have completed the training. This certificate can then be attached to subsequent job applications.

For this course, there is also the option of taking an examination for the "Six Sigma Yellow Belt" with an external examination provider (for a fee) after completing the course.

Summary and Outlook

The paper describes the demand and necessity for a transformation in teaching modes towards flipped classroom formats and/or certification course modules. To master the steps a literature review has been performed to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats arising from this methodical shift. Ideas and toolboxes can be found in the literature and can be used as a blueprint for the education and training of future industrial engineers. According to the findings FLiX research centre has developed a set of training courses and implemented them into their educational programs for both, students and business professionals on bachelor and master level.

Keeping the current industrial, social and ecological changes in mind the content development is rather dynamic. Besides looking for a suitable funding possibility, recommendations for further adjustments are welcome. A proposal is to set up a new online and onsite class to train the future European service engineers within a network of interested universities.

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Figures

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Internal	<p>The students can...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ...determine their own learning pace and repeat the content as often as they want. ✓ ...bring in their interests and preferences and acquire knowledge independently. ✓ ...can actively participate in class, expand their skills and check their learning progress. <p>The teacher can...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ...promote and challenge the students individually, recognize their strengths and weaknesses and offer differentiated learning opportunities. ✓ ...use the class time more effectively by focusing on the application and deepening of the content. ✓ ...increase the motivation and engagement of the students by giving them more autonomy and responsibility. 	<p>The students must ...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ...be willing to deal with the content before class and organize themselves. ✓ ...have the necessary technical and media requirements to access the learning materials. ✓ ...have the necessary learning strategies to understand, process and reflect on the content. <p>The teacher must...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ...carefully select, prepare and provide the learning materials. ✓ ...plan, design and moderate the learning activities in class. ✓ ...observe, evaluate and document the learning achievements of the students.
External	<p>The flipped classroom concept offers the opportunity to adapt the learning to...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ...the needs, interests and abilities of the students and to give them more self-determination and participation. ✓ ...the requirements of the digital and globalized world and to prepare the students for lifelong learning. ✓ ...the possibilities of modern technologies and to provide the students with diverse and innovative learning resources. 	<p>The flipped classroom concept entails the risk that the students...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ...will be overwhelmed or under-challenged if they have to acquire ...will be isolated or distracted if they acquire the content only through digital media and do not maintain social interactions. ✓ ...will learn inadequately or inappropriately if the content is not of high quality or didactically meaningful and no learning control takes place.

Figure 1: SWOT Analysis of Flipped Classroom Concepts

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Internal	<p>Certificate courses...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ...offer learners more flexibility and autonomy in choosing and organising their learning path. ✓ ...allow learners to deepen or broaden their knowledge and skills in specific areas without having to complete an entire study programme. ✓ ...increase the motivation and commitment of learners as they are tailored to their individual goals and needs. ✓ ...promote interdisciplinarity and the networking of learners with other subject areas and institutions. ✓ ...can serve as an incentive or recognition for learners' learning achievements by issuing them with a certificate or badge attesting to their competences. 	<p>Certificate courses...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ...require a high degree of self-organisation and personal responsibility from learners, which not all learners are able or willing to take on. ✓ ...can lead to learners being overwhelmed or lacking direction if they choose too many or too few courses or do not have a clear learning plan. ✓ ...can lead to fragmentation or isolation of the learning process if they are not embedded in a larger context or curriculum. ✓ ...can lead to a lack of uniformity or transparency in quality standards and learning outcomes if they are not offered or recognised by an accredited institution or organisation. ✓ ...may disadvantage or marginalise certain groups of learners if they are not accessible or affordable to all learners or if they require certain prerequisites or prior knowledge.
External	<p>Certificate courses can...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ...increase the attractiveness and relevance of student education by offering learners more choice and individualisation. ✓ ...can promote the adaptability and innovation of student education by providing learners with new topics and methods that respond to the current and future challenges and needs of society and the labour market. ✓ ...support the integration and diversification of student education by giving learners the opportunity to engage with different disciplines, cultures and perspectives and to learn from each other. ✓ ...improve the mobility and transferability of student education by giving learners the opportunity to use or recognise their certificates or badges in different contexts and institutions. ✓ ...ensure the sustainability and continuity of student education by giving learners the opportunity to promote and document their lifelong learning. 	<p>Certificate courses can...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ...lead to a devaluation or displacement of traditional student education if they are seen as substitutes or competitors for regular degree programmes or degrees. ✓ ...lead to a dilution or distortion of academic standards and content if they are too focussed on market demand or learning preferences and neglect academic quality or integrity. ✓ ...divide or fragment the academic community if they lead to competition or imbalance between different disciplines or institutions or hinder collaboration or exchange. ✓ ...lead to learner exploitation or inequity if they impose excessive costs or fees on learners or misuse or manipulate their data or performance. ✓ ...lead to learner uncertainty or dissatisfaction if they do not provide clear or reliable statements about learning objectives, the learning process or learning outcomes, or if they do not provide adequate support or guidance to learners.

Figure 2: SWOT Analysis of Certificate Course Modules

Figure 3. Service Engineering training course [source: own graph]

Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction • Business Models • Principles of Service Development • Design Thinking • Problem finding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphazise • Expert Interview • Mind Mapping • Define • Persona • Presentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ideation • Brainwriting • Value Propostion Canvas • Presentation
Day 4	Day 5	Day 6
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prototyping • Test • Improvement • Presentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7Ps marketing for services • Tiered pricing odel • Presentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation Service • Course evaluation Q&A • Examination • Certificates

Figure 4. Course content [source: own graph]